

EOSC-IF

EOSC Service Catalogue Interoperability Guidelines

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EOSC-IF / Service Catalogue Interoperability **Guidelines**

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Abstract

This EOSC Service Catalogue Interoperability Guidelines are the guidelines necessary for anyone that needs to interoperate with the EOSC Service Catalogue, an integral part of EOSC Resource Catalogue. These guidelines enable onboarding and management of Providers and Resources to the EOSC Resource Catalogue, but also exchange of Providers and Resources between the EOSC Resource Catalogue and other thematic or regional catalogues. The Interoperability Guidelines also include instructions for interactions between the EOSC Service Catalogue and other EOSC Core components.

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1. Glossary

EOSC Future project Glossary is incorporated by reference: <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/x/JOCK>

2. List of Abbreviations

Acronym	Definition
AARP	Authenticated and Authorised Representative of a Provide
COR	(External) Catalogue Owner Representative
EIAB	EOSC Interoperability Advisory Board
EPOT	EOSC Portal Onboarding Team
HLE	Hosting Legal Entity
IF	Interoperability Framework
PID	Persistent Identifier
RoP	Rules of Participation
PP	Privacy Policy
ToU	Terms Of Use
TRL	Technology Readiness Level

Table 1. Abbreviations

3. Intended Audience

This interoperability guideline is intended for adoption by:

- Admins that are responsible as representatives of Providers of Resources
- Catalogue Owners responsible for integrating their Catalogues with the EOSC Service Catalogue,
- Members of the EPOT team and the EOSC Interoperability Advisory Board
- EOSC Core Component tech leads / integrators
- Anyone else that needs to fetch public available data about Providers and Resources in EOSC Ecosystem

4. Description and main features

EOSC Service Catalogue, as part of the EOSC Resource Catalogue is the heart of the EOSC Future ecosystem. It provides both data and functionality to register, maintain, administer and share resources onboarded by various providers. Moreover, it's the point of reference for all EOSC Future components that provide added value to this information and help in making all this data and services searchable and accessible using various tools, both for researchers and end users.

The EOSC Resource Catalog is the result of merging the **EOSC Service Catalogue** (including data source services) and the EOSC Research Product Catalogue, together with the related list of EOSC providers. These are populated independently, as the resource onboarding process they support differs due to the different nature of the resources they manage, but their resources are interrelated. They can acquire metadata records from similar catalogues located within RI/clusters/other organisations premises or, in the case of research products, directly from the data sources. As a result, the EOSC Resource catalogue contains metadata about services, data sources, and research products, together with semantic relationships between them, highlighting the nature of the connection between services and products (e.g. hosted By, generated By, etc.)

This document presents the main integration and usage use cases for interacting with the EOSC Service Catalogue. It describes the current status of the components that consist of the EOSC Resource Catalog and its relations and it proposes interfaces as guidelines to be followed to achieve and/or extend the interoperability between these components necessary for the system to evolve to the EOSC Future requirements. Moreover, it proposes functionality that is required for the EOSC Resource Catalog to interact with other EOSC Future ecosystem components, such as Marketplace, Accounting, Monitoring etc, and to be able to disseminate information about resources to external collaborators and teams, such as thematic and regional data/services catalogues .

More specifically, the EOSC Service Catalogue functionality is offered through two distinct software components:

EOSC Providers Portal : the portal enables the front-end functionality for the registration of EOSC Providers, organisations entitled to publish their resources via the EOSC Catalogue, and offers them capabilities to onboard and manage EOSC resources. It also offers the Provider dashboard, where representatives from provider organisations have a detailed view on their offerings in the EOSC portal as well as various usage statistics on their resources. Finally, it offers to members of the onboarding team of the EOSC portal the functionality to manage the EOSC portal catalogue entries, i.e., manage the onboarding process of providers that apply to list their resources in the portal, audit on the onboarded resources, etc.

EOSC Service Registry: the component offers the underlying storage functionality and the interoperability tools for the programmatic access, registration, manage (CRUD) of providers, services, and catalogues. It also offers the necessary API functionality for the interoperability of service catalogues from individual providers or aggregators (e.g., thematic, or regional catalogues) with the EOSC portal. Modifications to the entities maintained in the Service Catalogue are synchronised with the EOSC Research Graph, which aggregates the complete set of entities and their relationships in the EOSC portal.

5. Response to Community Need

Regarding service/resource onboarding and management, EOSC Service Catalogue should provide functionality for:

- providers, to register to the EOSC to become eligible to the onboarding of resources
- providers, to onboard their services/research products into the EOSC Service Data
- providers, to view the list of services registered in the EOSC portal and perform a variety of actions such as activate, deactivate, view usage statistics,
- EOSC Portal Onboarding Team (EPOT) members, to manage the onboarding process (approve, reject an application), manage the catalogue of providers and services and audit the validity of the catalogue entries.
- providers of catalogues, to add regional or thematic catalogues to the EOSC ecosystem

Regarding resources discovery and access, EOSC Service Catalogue should provide functionality for:

- APIs to search, browse, and navigate the EOSC Resources and Providers
- APIs to broker/route metadata information to service providers and any other EOSC future component that uses such data [3][7].

6. High-level Service Architecture

This is the general architecture of the EOSC Resource Catalogue and subcomponent interactions:

Figure 1. Resource Catalogue High Level Architecture

EOSC Service Catalogue : EOSC Service Catalogue is the repository component offering the necessary programmatic interfaces for the addition, modification, and access to information regarding providers, resources and user activity collected in EOSC portal

EOSC Providers Portals: EOSC Providers Portals components offer front-end functionality to users representing a Provider organisation, who wish to onboard their organisation and onboard resources in the EOSC Resource Catalogue, to manage and customise the way offerings are presented to end users and finally to gain insights on a multitude of usage statistics, user-generated events and statistics collected.

EOSC Research Product Catalogue: The Research Product Catalogue is a public and open access collection of metadata and semantic links (~1Bi) between research-related entities collected from data sources (2400+) or inferred from PDFs (14Mi+). Entities are *research products*, namely articles (124M+), datasets (14Mi+), software (200K+), and other research products (8Mi+), *organisations* (250,000), *funders* (~25), *funding streams*, *projects* (3.5Mi+), *research communities* (7), and *data sources* (~80K).

7. Definitions

No specialist terms were used in this document.

8. Licensing Information

Use of the Service Catalogue functionality and data is subject to Terms of Use by the Authenticated and Authorised Representative of Providers, as described here: <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/EOSCF/Terms+of+Use>

9. Related Guidelines

Resource Type	Title	Short Description	relatedIdentifier
Service	OpenAIRE Explore	A comprehensive and open dataset of research information	https://explore.openaire.eu/
Service	EOSC Monitoring	Architecture and Interoperability Guidelines for using the Monitoring infrastructure	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7118591
Service	EOSC Helpdesk	Architecture and Interoperability Guidelines for using the Helpdesk system	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7308617

Table 2. Related Guidelines

10. Adopted Standards

The following tables list the standards, API and protocols used.

Standard	Short description	References
REST	Loosely adhere to the REST paradigm.	https://www.ics.uci.edu/~fielding/pubs/dissertation/rest_arch_style.htm
JSON API	A specification for building APIs in JSON format	https://jsonapi.org/
Handle System	Handle System Overview	https://www.rfc-editor.org/rfc/rfc3650.txt

Table 3. Adopted standards

Protocol/API	Short description	References
HTTPS	TLS secured HTTP	https://tools.ietf.org/html/rfc2818
HTTP / JMX / Shell / SQL ...	All the plugins should be based on standard protocols or formats	http://software.in2p3.fr/lavoisier/adaptors.html
JMS	API for accessing enterprise messaging systems from Java programs.	https://docs.oracle.com/cd/E19957-01/816-5904-10/816-5904-10.pdf
Spring Data API	Used for all CRUD operation implementation in EOSC Service Catalogue	https://docs.spring.io/spring-data/jpa/docs/current/reference/html/#reference
ePIC API	European Persistent Identifier Consortium Documentation, used for creating and assigning PIDs to resources	https://epic.grnet.gr/docs/

Table 4. Adopted Protocols/APIs

11. Integration Options

There are three main cases regarding interaction with the Service Catalogue:

- Onboarding single Providers and Resources directly to the EOSC Service Catalogue
- Onboarding entire collections of Providers and Resources as parts of third party external Catalogues (Regional/Thematic catalogues, etc.)
- Interoperations with other EOSC Future components

User Authentication and Token-based Access to the APIs

In the case of REST API interoperations, users can obtain an API token for the secured methods by logging in and visiting the EOSC AAI webpage for issuing a token. <https://aai.eosc-portal.eu/providers-api>. The following form request a consent from users regarding the permissions granted to this service. Figure shows the authorization screen for providers to generate an API token for use in the EOSC APIs

Figure 2. Authorization screen for providers to generate an API token

There are two types of tokens. The Access token is used in every call of a method requiring authorization. It has a duration of an hour, after this period, the user should issue a new one and use it in the APIs.

The Refresh token is used for generating new Access Tokens. The refresh token lasts for 12 months. Figure 7 shows the screen that allows users to generate and copy the tokens in their API calls.

Figure 3. API Tokens generation

Deployments / environments

Regarding the Service Catalogue deployments, currently there are three different environments which can be used by resource providers

Production: <https://providers.eosc-portal.eu/openapi> : All API calls update the registry and retrieve the live contents. It is the endpoint where production systems should communicate.

Sandbox: <https://sandbox.providers.eosc-portal.eu/openapi> : It is a Stable Replica of production. Used as a playground for API and end users. API calls do not update the registry and it is the recommended starting point for the users who wish to explore *the current version of the APIs*.

Beta: <https://beta.providers.eosc-portal.eu/openapi> : It is the beta environment where new features and API methods are early released. API calls do not update the registry and it is the recommended starting point for users who wish to explore *the upcoming releases of the APIs*.

12. Interoperability Guidelines

This section presents the main integration and usage use cases for the EOSC Service Catalogue, regarding resource publishing and management, Service Catalogue onboarding and synchronisation, resource graph maintenance, and interoperations with other EOSC Future components, such as Marketplace etc.

This is the general onboarding path and actions of a Resource to the EOSC Service Catalogue:

Figure 4. Onboarding and managing a Resource in the Service Catalogue

Provider/Resource onboarding and management

EOSC Service Catalogue offers **two** interfaces to enable onboarding and management of providers and resources:

1. The EOSC Providers Portal Component: a **web portal** that offers a simple UI to interact with the EOSC Service Catalogue.
2. The EOSC Service Catalogue **REST API**

These interfaces enable the following functionalities:

- Onboarding service, which implements the EOSC portal onboarding process for resources, i.e., the registration of a new Provider and the registration of Resources or Data sources managed by the Providers, as well as the registration of catalogues. Onboarding services will target authenticated users

who will be able to onboard either via a web-based step wise process or programmatically by using the EOSC Service Catalogue's APIs.

- Resource Management service: It offers the functionality for authenticated users from providers to manage their resource portfolio in the catalogue, i.e., view the list of resources associated with their organisation and manage all characteristics of their offerings. Resource management will enable users from onboarded providers to add, update a resource , also the ability enable providers to "activate"/"deactivate" a resource in the EOSC Portal, to assign it to categories or other classification schemes (e.g., scientific domain, TRL, etc), to manage the different versions of a resource and add new users who will be responsible for managing the offerings of a provider.
- Providers Dashboard: It serves as the UI entry point for providers. The dashboard offers an overview to the users for the list of the providers and it represents the list of resources and their properties including a history of changes applied to each resource. The dashboard will also give access to a rich set of statistics, which are collected by the EOSC portal and will be associated with resources and providers onboarded in the EOSC Service Catalogue.
- Statistics over the content of the catalogue, organised by resources and providers, such as number of resources per scientific discipline, providers per country, etc. These include usage statistics, such as views and visits for a resource, aggregated views and visits for all resources offered by a provider, search related statistics which are associated with a provider, orders placed for a resource, ratings,

recommendations offered to users related to a resource and finally favourites those users add in the EOSC portal.

- Validation/Auditing functionality for recurring quality assurance of resources data and status and for curation of providers changes on resources over time. This functionality is currently used by EPOT Team members, but it also applies to external catalogues administrators.

In a nutshell, functionality offered includes:

- For providers
 - Onboarding
 - Management of resources
 - Live usage statistics from the EOSC Providers Portal
 - Email notifications
 - Interaction with EPOT team
- For EPOT team members
 - Onboarding management
 - Auditing and Catalogue management
 - Email digest and interaction with providers
- For other users (funders, EOSC profiles management (vocabularies, schema, etc.)
 - Statistics

EOSC Providers Portal offers a web UI for the providers to use for onboarding their services. Onboarding process steps are the following:

1. A service provider admin adds a new service provider
2. Portal admin approves (or rejects) the service provider
3. If approved, service provider submits a service template
4. Portal admin approves (or rejects) the service template
5. If template is approved, service provider is granted access to the dashboard to manage owned services

As mentioned, onboarding and management can also be achieved through the REST API offered by the EOSC Service Catalogue component. This is the current status for REST APIs:

Client	API	Resource Profile	Status
Services	<p>For Service Providers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provider/Resource/Controlled Vocabulary REST API • Onboarding workflow (guide, documentation) <p>For EPOT team members:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Auditing and Onboarding workflow • Email digest and interaction with providers 	Resource/Provider Profiles (v 3.0, v 4.0)	<p>Profiles v3.0 deployed in Production until June 2022</p> <p>Profiles v4.0 deployed</p> <p>Next Profiles version TBA</p>
Data Sources	<p>For Data Source Providers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • REST APIs for Data Source Providers/Resources/Controlled Vocabularies <p>For EPOT team members</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Onboarding/Auditing workflow for data sources 	Data Source Profiles (v.4.0)	To be released end of April 2023
Training Resources	<p>For Training Resource Providers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • REST APIs for Training Resource Providers/Resources/Controlled Vocabularies <p>For EPOT team members</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Onboarding/Auditing workflow for training resources 	TBA	To be released end of April 2023

Interoperability Guidelines	<p><i>For Interoperability Guidelines Providers:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>REST APIs for Interoperability Guideline Providers/Resources/Controlled Vocabularies</i> <p><i>For EPOT team members</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Onboarding/Auditing workflow for Interoperability Guidelines</i> 	TBA	<i>To be released end of April 2023</i>
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Table 5. REST APIs

An overview of the methods offered by each controller is shown in the next table. Note that the resource and provider controllers offer functionality for adding (POST) and updating (PUT) information in the Service Catalogue.

Controller	Type	Method Name	Description	Require Authentication [A1] [A2]
Resource	POST	/resource	Adds, i.e. registers, a new resource in the Catalogue	Y
	PUT	/resource	Updates an existing resource description	Y
	POST	/resource /validate	Validates the registration or update of a resource without it actually being added/modified in the Catalogue	Y
	GET	/resource/{id}	Gets the most current version of a specific resource providing the ID	N

	GET	/resource/all	Filters a list of resources based on a set of filters	N
	GET	/resource/by/{field}	Gets all resources in the catalogue organised by a field, e.g. get organised in categories	N
	GET	/resource/byID/{ids}	Gets a list of resources based on a set of IDs	N
	GET	/resource/{id}/{version}	Gets a past version of a specific resource providing the ID and a version identifier	N
Provider	PUT	/provider	Updates provider info	Y
	GET	/provider/all	Gets a list of all resource providers in the catalogue	N
	GET	/provider/{id}	Gets provider's data given the provider id	N
	GET	/provider/{id}/services	Gets a list of resources offered by a provider	N
Vocabulary	GET	/vocabulary/byType/{type}	Gets a list of all vocabularies with their terms	N
	GET	/vocabulary/{id}	Gets the description of s specific term given its Id	N

Table 6. Common REST API requests for Provider and Resource management and operations

Sample API usage guidelines

This section provides guidelines – in the form of a step-by-step example – for a provider to start using the API for adding and updating resource information in the EOSC Portal. These guidelines are indicative examples for the API-based implementation of the Use Cases presented in Section 3. They are available in the API documentation page (<https://providers.eosc-portal.eu/developers>) and they will be updated according to the evolution of the APIs.

Add a new Resource

Step 1. Start from the documentation, i.e. <https://eosc-portal.eu/providers-documentation> regarding the EOSC profiles and the onboarding process as well as the API documentation in <https://providers.eosc-portal.eu/openapi>

Step 2. Follow the onboarding process and Register your organisation in EOSC-Portal.

Step 3. Export one or more of the resources to JSON according to the EOSC Profiles.

For indicative examples of Resource and Provider represented as JSON objects according to the EOSC Profiles, see the aforementioned Open API link.

Step 4. Using the AAI service (<https://aai.eosc-portal.eu/providers-api>) of the EOSC Portal, login and retrieve a new API token.

Any subsequent request to the API using that cookie, is authenticated.

Step 5. Validate the resource description

Validate that the resource is well formed by calling the **POST/resource/validate** method.

Step 6. Make a POST resource call to add the new resource in the catalogue.

Upon success you get a new resource ID.

Step 7. The new resource is registered and visible in the Providers Dashboard[2] and the EOSC Marketplace. You may validate the addition by calling the **GET/resource/{id}** and providing the resource id.

Update of an existing Resource / Provider

Repeat Steps 1-5.

Step 6. Make a **PUT/resource (or PUT/provider)** call to update the resource / provider in the catalogue.

Upon success you get the resource ID / provider ID

Step 7. The resource / provider entry is updated and visible in the EOSC Portal. You may validate the update by calling the **GET/resource/{id}** (**GET/provider/{id}**)

Retrieval of Resources / Providers from the Registry

Make a **GET/resource/all (or GET/provider/all)** to retrieve the list of resources / providers in the registry.

Select one of the resource / providers and using the id value make a **GET/resource/{id}** (or **GET/provider/{id}**) to retrieve the details of this resource / provider.

Make a **GET /resource/all?query=CESSDA** (by putting a keyword as parameter) to retrieve all resources containing the CESSDA keyword in their description (e.g., provider name, resource description, etc).

Make a **GET resource/by/trl** to get all resources in the registry and organize them by their TRL values (e.g. TRL6,7,8,9)

The base URL for the use of these methods is <https://api.eosc-portal.eu/>. For example, the method **/resource/all** can be used calling <https://api.eosc-portal.eu/resource/all>

Resource catalogues onboarding and management (Third party, Thematic or Regional)

This functionality facilitates the onboarding of entire collections or **Catalogues** of resources maintained by another organisation or provider. These catalogues could include resources that share a common subject (thematic catalogues) or resources that come from a specific geographical region or consortium/fellowship (regional catalogues). There are three key issues that distinguish resource catalogue registration from a simple resource registration as already described above:

- A service or resource can participate in more than one catalogues
- A catalogue should be able to synchronise data with the EOSC Resource catalogue (vice and versa)
- A catalogue should be managed by a provider, just as any other resource

A catalogue can be considered as another kind of EOSC service. Like all other services, it is managed by a Catalogue Owner (the entity registering the catalogue to the EOSC catalogue). This means that:

- EOSC catalogue has its own entry to itself
- EOSC is a Provider, managing the EOSC Catalogue

Resources and Providers onboarded through a third party catalogue contain a reference to the original hosting catalogue. Those registered directly in EOSC Catalogue could mention EOSC Catalogue, while those harvested/aggregated/collected/registered by other catalogues mention the respective catalogue.

The proposed procedure of onboarding catalogues to EOSC Service Catalogue should have the following general steps:

- Register catalogue
- Approve catalogue
- Start pushing services and providers (using REST API calls).

After the onboarding, synchronisation may be set up to automatically import records into the EOSC Providers Portal. It is for this reason a separate procedure is needed to cover the onboarding of External Catalogue.

In general, catalogues are added after initial approval, and EOSC Service Catalogue does the housekeeping on the "who-on-who" (which services/providers are on which catalogue). Catalogue providers can trigger updates

through Messaging on REST API . In the general case, all REST API calls from the previous use case could be used for managing a catalogue as another case of EOSC Service Catalogue resource.

Figure 5. Catalogue onboarding/updating

Again, EOSC Service Catalogue (as part of the EOSC Resource Catalogue) offers two interfaces to enable onboarding and management of providers and resources from third party catalogues:

1. the EOSC Service Catalogue REST APIs and
2. the EOSC Providers Portal Component.

Steps for initial catalogue onboarding are the following:

Step 1: The Catalogue Owner Representative (COR) onboards the Catalogue into the EOSC Portal. The COR logs on to the Portal and may proceed with the onboarding of a Catalogue via the web interface.

Step 2: The COR asserts he/she is an Authorised Representative of a Catalogue Owner. By clicking on "Add a Catalogue" the COR is asked a) to agree to the EOSC Portal Privacy Policy and b) to assert to be an authorised representative of the Catalogue.

Once a) and b) are accepted and the latter asserted, the COR can apply to onboard the Catalogue

Step 3: The COR proceeds to fill in the Catalogue profile. The COR completes the Catalogue Profile ([currently v.4.00 EOSC-Multi Provider Catalogue](#))

Automated mechanisms are used to the greatest extent possible to ensure that all required information is included and that the information is of the correct type, size, etc. those checks are the same checks that apply

when entering values regarding URLs, images used as logos, contact emails, etc. More specifically, for the Catalogue onboarding case:

- Catalogue website URL should be a valid and existing URL and relating to the catalogue itself
- Logo URL should be a valid and existing direct URL, without using redirects
- Legal Entity - the Catalogue Owner should be a Legal Entity or should refer to a Hosting Legal Entity chosen from the HLE controlled vocabulary
- Contact and Admin email fields should be properly formatted email values
- Phones should comply to Phone formatting rules/length
- Mandatory fields should be all filled
- Text fields should be filled with values with proper length, as indicated per case.

In case any difficulties arise during the application, the COR may communicate issues to the EPOT via email onboarding@eosc-portal.eu.

If the form is completed and passes all automatic checks, it can be submitted.

Step 4: The EPOT reviews the newly onboarded Catalogue

Step 5: The Catalogue is now approved and the COR can push Providers and Resources to it using REST API calls as illustrated in the single provider/resource onboarding (but using the proper **catalogue_id** parameter).

For example, to add a new resource, a POST API call would be used:

```
curl -X POST --header 'Content-Type: application/json' --header 'Accept: application/json' -d '<service_ID>' 'https://api.eosc-portal.eu/catalogue/<catalogue_ID>/resource'
```

...

Automatic validations for records pushed from external Catalogues to the EOSC Catalogue include:

- URL fields should be valid and existing
- Logo URLs should be valid and existing direct URLs, without using redirects
- Contact and Admin and other email fields should be properly formatted email values
- Phones should comply to Phone formatting rules/length
- Mandatory fields should be all filled
- Text fields should be filled with values with proper length, as indicated per case.

Interoperability functionalities described above for individual Providers and Services apply also for Services and Providers originating from third party Catalogues, and for Catalogues themselves. Specifically, Catalogues as entities should be approved by the EPOT Team or become members of the EOSC Federation so as to be able to access EOSC Resource Catalogue. This is the current status for REST APIs:

<p>Third party Resource Catalogues</p>	<p><i>For third party EOSC Federated Catalogues:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Catalogue Provider/Resource/Controlled Vocabularies REST API</i> <p><i>For EPOT team members:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Auditing and Registry workflow</i> 	<p><u>Catalogue Resource Profiles (v.4.0)</u></p>	<p><i>Deployed in Beta</i></p> <p><i>(Catalogue onboarding released July 2022, complete resource/provider push-pull and deduplication support available since September 2022)</i></p>
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Table 7. Catalogue REST API

Interaction with other EOSC Future components – Marketplace, Monitoring, Helpdesk, etc

The EOSC Service Catalogue uses a JMS messaging subsystem in order to facilitate a loose coupling communication with Marketplace. This can be expanded for use to more EOSC components and/or external systems that seek interaction with EOSC Resource Catalog (for example, external catalogues). JMS messaging can be replaced by AMS messaging for greater scalability, and a more general specification about message format and schema might be necessary to cover more component interactions.

Integration with other EOSC Core Components - Monitoring and Helpdesk

Providers can specify endpoints and info regarding **Monitoring** and **Helpdesk** functionality for specific resources:

The screenshot shows a web form titled "Helpdesk Extension" for the service "mantosat_test.mantesat_1st_service". The form includes a dropdown menu for "Guidelines for" set to "Direct Usage". It has three main sections: "Service" with a text input containing "AGROINFO Service" and a "+ Add Service" button; "Group (*)" with a text input containing "Group A" and a "+ Add Group" button; and "Organisation" with a text input containing "An Org". A note at the top states: "Fields with (*) are mandatory and must be completed in order to save this form."

Figure 6. Providers Portal form for Monitoring integration

Information for Monitoring or Helpdesk integration can be provided during onboarding or at a later stage, either through the Providers Portal UI (using forms similar to the one in Figure 4) or through REST API calls.

Users and providers can see monitoring metrics for resources reliability and can benefit from a single helpdesk for any issue across the EOSC ecosystem

Type	Method Name	Description	Require Authentication[A1] [A2]
POST	/service-extensions/helpdesk	Creates a new Helpdesk endpoint.	Y
PUT	/service-extensions/helpdesk	Updates the Helpdesk endpoint with the given id.	Y
POST	/service-extensions/monitoring	Creates a new Monitoring endpoint.	Y
PUT	/service-extensions/monitoring	Updates the Monitoring endpoint with the given id.	Y
DELETE	/service-extensions/helpdesk/{catalogueId}/{serviceId}	Deletes the Helpdesk endpoint of the specific Service of the specific Catalogue.	Y
DELETE	/service-extensions/monitoring/{catalogueId}/{serviceId}	Deletes the Monitoring endpoint of the specific Service of the specific Catalogue	Y
GET	/service-extensions/helpdesk/all	Filter a list of Helpdesk endpoints based on a set of filters or get a list of all Helpdesks endpoints in the Catalogue	N

GET	/service-extensions/helpdesk/byService/{serviceId}	Returns the Helpdesk endpoint of the given Service of the given Catalogue	N
PUT	/service-extensions/helpdesk/{id}	Returns the Helpdesk endpoint with the given id	Y
GET	/service-extensions/monitoring/all	Filter a list of Monitorings endpoints based on a set of filters or get a list of all Monitorings endpoints in the Catalogue	N
GET	/service-extensions/monitoring/byService/{serviceId}	Returns the Monitoring endpoint of the given Service of the given Catalogue	N
GET	/service-extensions/monitoring/serviceTypes	Returns all the available Monitoring endpoint serviceTypes	N
GET	/service-extensions/monitoring/{id}	Returns the Monitoring endpoint with the given id	N

Table 9. Common REST API requests for Core Functionality operations

13.Examples of solutions implementing this specification

Onboarding using the Providers Portal

The screenshot shows the 'Providers Portal' interface for onboarding a provider. The header includes navigation links: 'Contact Us', 'Portal Home', 'Catalogue & Marketplace', 'Providers Dashboard' (active), 'Providers Documentation', 'Thanassis Mantes' (user profile), and 'Logout'. Below the header is the 'EUROPEAN OPEN SCIENCE CLOUD' logo and navigation links: 'Statistics', 'For Providers', and 'For Catalogues'. A message states: 'Fields with (*) are mandatory and must be completed in order to save this form. Leaving optional fields blank will remove the relevant heading from the published resource/provider profile.' There are links for 'Do you need help?' and 'Download as PDF/Excel'. The main content area is titled 'Provider Profile Information Blocks' and features a sidebar with 9 blocks: 1. Basic (*), 2. Marketing (*), 3. Classification, 4. Location (*), 5. Contact (*), 6. Maturity, 7. Dependencies, 8. Other, and 9. Admins (*). A progress bar shows '5 of 5' completed blocks. The main form fields are: 'Name (*)' (Full Name of the Provider/Organisation offering Resources and acting as main contact point for the Resources) with the value 'Aerospace Logistics Technology Engineering Company' and a suggested length of 100 characters; 'Abbreviation (*)' (Abbreviation of the Provider Name) with the value 'ALTEC' and a suggested length of 30 characters; 'Website (*)' (Website with information about the Provider) with the value 'https://www.altecspace.it'; and 'Legal Entity (*)' (Is the Provider a Legal Entity?) with radio buttons for 'No' and 'Yes' (selected).

Figure 7. Onboarding a Provider from the Providers Portal

Step 1: Log in to the Providers Portal and agree to the RoP

Step 2: Apply for becoming a Provider. Fill in Providers Profile forms

Step 3: After approval by EPOT, the first service can be registered. Resource profile forms need to be filled and validated

Step 4: After approval, register more services in Providers Dashboard

Step 5: Done! (but EPOT will regularly review resources for quality)

Service Catalogue Resource onboarding through the API in steps

The most common use case for integration with the Service Catalogue is the onboarding of a service through the API. The following steps describe this procedure beginning with no providers onboarded and ending with a resource being onboarded through the Service Catalogue API

Step 1: The Representative of the Provider visits the Portal

A Representative of the Provider visits the "For Providers" Section of the EOSC Portal (<https://providers.eosc-portal.eu/becomeAProvider>) and clicks on "Become a provider! Apply now" (<https://providers.eosc-portal.eu/provider/add>) to start the process of applying to become a Provider.

Step 2: The Representative of the Provider registers with the Portal using an existing identity from a supported Social or Academic AAI mechanism

Step 3: The Authenticated Representative of the Provider logs into the Portal

At this point the Provider Representative is now an Authenticated and Authorised Representative of the Provider (or **AARP**).

Step 4: The Authenticated and Authorised Representative of a Provider applies to onboard the Provider.

Registering a single provider is **not open to use through API** and is only possible by **filling in the form at the Providers Portal webpage**. (However, after initial onboarding of the Provider, the AARP can update provider details using the respective PUT call:

```
curl -X PUT --header 'Content-Type: application/json' --header 'Accept: application/json' --header 'Authorization: <token>' -d '<provider_data>' '<service_catalogue_env_hostname>/provider?catalogue_id=<catalogue_id>'
```

As said above, the AARP may apply for the onboarding of the Provider by completing the mandatory fields of the Provider Profile, marked with (*). (The Profile is available to download and preview in various formats [here](#)).

Step 5: The Portal Onboarding Team reviews the newly onboarded Provider and then the AARP gets access to the Portal Dashboard.

Step 6: The Authenticated and Authorised Representative of a Provider applies to onboard its first Resource or Datasource via the API.

The AARP may apply for the onboarding of the **first Resource** by using the Providers Portal Open API. For this, the Provider needs to get an Authorization token from Providers Portal [API Token](#) webpage.

The Provider (or Catalog) Admins obtain an Access and a Refresh token by signing into the AAI service of the EOSC Portal.

- Access tokens are valid for 1 hour
- Refresh Tokens are valid for 12 months

Access token is used in the Authorization header when making requests to the EOSC Portal.

- The token is **required** when pushing information with PUT\PUSH methods
- The token is **not required** in GET methods.

After getting the access token, the provider can call a POST method to onboard the first resource:

```
curl -X POST --header 'Content-Type: application/json' --header 'Accept: application/json' --header 'Authorization: <token>' -d '<resource_data>' '<service_catalogue_env_hostname>/resource'
```

Step 7: The EOSC Portal Onboarding Team reviews the newly onboarded resource.

For the first resource of a provider to be onboarded, the EPOT examines whether it has been already onboarded by any other Providers and if this the case, tries to resolve the issue. The EPOT examines the quality of the metadata, if they follow the general recommendations and guidance of the Resource Profile, spelling, accuracy, composition and URLs. If the Resource description does not comply with the minimum requirements of the Portal and the rules and criteria based on the current RoP and the typology of the Resource Profile, the AARP may be asked to take action.

Step 8: Onboarding more resources, updating and deleting

If the first resource is approved, then more Resources can be onboarded, updated or deleted through API (via POST, PUT and DELETE /resource calls) without further need for approval by the EPOT. Note that onboarded providers and resources are periodically audited for validation and quality checking by the EPOT.

For details on how to use the API, one may visit the [OpenAPI page](#) of the Providers Portal.

14. References

- [1] EOSC Service Catalogue OpenAPI Documentation Available at <https://providers.eosc-portal.eu/openapi>
- [2] EOSC Providers Hub. Available at <https://eosc-portal.eu/eosc-providers-hub>
- [3] EOSC Providers Portal. Available at <https://providers.eosc-portal.eu/home>
- [4] OpenAIRE Explore. 2023 [online] Available at <<https://explore.openaire.eu/>>
- [5] Access Level. OpenAIRE Guidelines v3. 2023. Available at https://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest/literature/field_accesslevel.html